

Callus production and plant regeneration efficiency in *Oryza* species, Tamil Nadu, India.

Species and cultivar	Seeds inoculated (no.)	Seeds (no.) with callus	Callus production ^a (%)	Calli inoculated (no.)	Regenerating calli (no.)	Regeneration efficiency ^b (%)
<i>O. spontanea</i>	68	26	38.2	42	12	28.5
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	73	40	54.5	42	9	21.4
<i>O. sativa</i>						
Cultivar Co 43	62	15	24.6	24	2	4.5
Cultivar IR50	68	42	61.7	44	18	40.9
Cultivar IR1552	72	39	54.2	36	7	19.4

^aCallus production (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of seeds with callus}}{\text{no. of seeds inoculated}} \times 100$. ^bRegeneration (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of regeneration calli}}{\text{no. of calli inoculated}} \times 100$.

regeneration frequencies are given in the table.

The banding patterns of esterase isozymes could be utilized as markers in in vitro studies by correlating banding patterns with frequencies of callus induction and regeneration. □

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Disease resistance

Reaction of selected cultivars to tungro (RTV) and other diseases in Tamil Nadu

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All locally grown cultivars were severely damaged by RTV in 1984. We screened

newly selected breeding lines for resistance to RTV using the vector green leafhoppers for artificial inoculation at 10 d. Lines showing 0-10% infection were compared with popular local varieties ADT36, CO 37 (Vaigai), White Ponni, and IR20 in the field.

Six lines (IR32429-148-1-3-3, IR35366-90-3-2-1-2[IR72], IR37865-29-3-1-3, IR39357-91-3-2-3, TNAU831520, and TNAU831521) were least infected with leaf blast (0-2 grade), neck blast (1.6 to 12.8%), and brown spot (1-3 grade) and showed sheath rot moderate infection (3-5 grade). The four popular local varieties showed high RTV

infection with artificial inoculation but moderate resistance to other diseases in the field. The yield potential of the six cultivars was comparable with that of the local varieties, or even better (see table). □

A conceptual model of disease resistance in rice pathosystems, and its implications for evaluating resistance

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We developed a conceptual model to focus understanding of quantitative resistance, defined as the ability of a host population to limit disease intensity. Quantitative resistance in rice usually consists of two components: the efficiency of qualitative resistance to eliminate the avirulent portion of the available inoculum and partial resistance to lower disease infection caused by virulent isolates (Fig. 1).

Partial resistance is best measured by challenging a population of rice plants with selected virulent isolate(s) alone, avoiding exogenous inoculum (alloinfection). A variety with

Yield and reaction to diseases of rice lines in Tamil Nadu, India.

Line or variety	Plants infected with RTV ^a (%)	Leaf blast ^b (grade)	Neck blast ^b (%)	Sheath rot ^b (grade)	Brown spot ^b (grade)	Mean yield (t/ha)
IR32429-148-1-3-3	0.0	2	3.3	3	3	5.7
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2 (IR72)	0.0	0	2.0	3	1	6.8
IR37865-29-3-1-3	10.0	0	12.8	5	2	5.1
IR39357-91-3-2-3	10.0	2	7.8	3	3	6.1
TNAU831520	6.3	0	1.4	5	3	5.9
TNAU831521	5.9	0	1.6	5	3	6.4
Local checks						
ADT36	70.0	0	19.4	5	3	5.1
CO 37	50.0	0	20.0	5	2	5.5
White Ponni	20.0	3	—	3	3	4.9
IR20	66.7	3	12.5	5	2	5.2

^aArtificial inoculation. ^bField infection under natural conditions.

1. Conceptual model illustrating the relationship between quantitative resistance to rice diseases and its components under natural pathosystem, IRRI, 1988. Presence of at least one compatible isolate is assumed.

2. General response curve of rice genotypes with differing levels of quantitative resistance (Q_nR) to rice disease potential levels, IRRI, 1988. VL = very low Q_nR , L = low, M = moderate, H = high, VH = very high.

quantitative resistance composed of high levels of two components will likely prove to have durable resistance, especially if pathogen isolates with virulence genes matched to genes for qualitative resistance have a low fitness in a given pathosystem.

The disease potential (pressure) in a particular crop is the sum of all varietal, agronomical, and edaphoclimatic conditions that affect the disease. No standard method to quantify disease potential has been developed yet. Nevertheless, disease potential can be estimated indirectly on the basis of disease severity in a cultivar chosen for

its intermediate partial resistance and low qualitative resistance. That cultivar will reflect changes over a wide range of disease potentials. Actual severity corresponding to low, moderate, or high disease levels will vary, depending upon the kind of disease.

The model in Figure 2 shows the response curves of varieties with different levels of quantitative resistance at different disease potential levels.

The terms "high" or "low" quantitative resistance are often used without clear definition. In our conceptual model, varieties with low or very low levels of quantitative resistance can be defined as those whose disease severity reaches maximum at low disease potential. Varieties with high or very high levels of quantitative resistance are those whose response curves only reach maximum at a very high disease potential (which may be rare under field conditions).

The relative differences between cultivars with different levels of

quantitative resistance will vary, depending on the disease potential (Fig. 2). Mass screenings of unknown genotypes can be made under moderate disease potential; fine differentiation among resistant cultivars should be made under moderately high disease potential. Under low disease potential, only low or very low levels of resistance can be differentiated.

Under high disease potential, varieties known to have high quantitative resistance suffer almost the same disease severity as known susceptible varieties. However, a remarkable difference in disease severity can be observed between cultivars with varying levels of resistance if disease potential is reduced (such as can be done with chemicals or by modifying cultural practices).

Quantitative resistance can therefore be a valuable component in integrated disease management, although it may not be sufficient by itself to control disease in certain agroclimatic regions. □

A method for scoring resistance to tungro (RTV)

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We used correlations between symptom severity and grain yield reduction to develop an effective scoring method for evaluating varieties for resistance to or tolerance for RTV infection.

Seedlings of nine varieties exposed to RTV-viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLHs) were transplanted in pots. Plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform virus and rice tungro spherical virus (RTBV + RTSV), with RTBV alone, and with RTSV alone were identified by latex serology 1 or 2 wk after inoculation (WAI). Plant height was measured and symptoms were recorded 3 WAI.

Height and yield reductions were generally low in Balimau Putih, Palasithari, Sigadis, and Utri Rajapan, but high in BW272-6B, FK135, and TN1 (see table). Plants infected with

RTBV + RTSV had healthy appearances in Balimau Putih, light green coloration in Utri Rajapan, mild yellowing in Sigadis and Palasithari, and severe yellow-orange discoloration in the other varieties. RTBV-infected plants generally showed milder discoloration than doubly infected plants. RTSV-infected plants showed no discoloration and very mild stunting. Irrespective of variety, plants infected with RTBV + RTSV had the greatest reduction in height and yield followed by RTBV-infected plants. The correlations between yield and height reductions among plants infected with RTBV + RTSV or with RTBV or RTSV alone were significant in BW272-6B, FK135, and TN1, but not in Balimau Putih, Sigadis, and Utri Rajapan. Apparently, plants with severe symptoms had greater yield reduction.

These results indicate that the level of tolerance for RTV can be scored at about 3-4 WAI on the basis of plant height reduction and degree of leaf discoloration.